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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF FISHERY COOPERATIVE INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted based on a literature study of several articles and books, carried out from July 2020 to September 2020. The writing of this article was done by collecting information from various sources, analyzing and then concluding. The existence of fisheries cooperatives is very helpful in meeting the needs of its members and the surrounding community such as basic assistance, capital, credit, or borrowing, sales, fishermen's needs in fishing and so on. The existence of cooperatives also provides benefits in other fields, such as education, development of community infrastructure, health and various community activities, especially fishermen.

INTRODUCTION

Many problems faced, the fisheries sector. such as physical damage to coastal and aquatic ecosystem habitats, decreasing water quality, overfishing, low handling and processing of fishery products, unstable prices for production factors, increasingly fierce market competition, poverty and capital problems. In addition, the low quality of human resources and mastery of technology also adds to the problem of fisheries development. For fishermen who are faced with various problems and obstacles in carrying out fishery activities which are their main activities. One of the community forums that can accommodate and distribute various activities that can support fisheries actors is fishery cooperatives. Article 33 of the 1945 Constitution states that there are three important elements in the Indonesian economy, namely state enterprises, private enterprises, and cooperatives. According to Pratiwi, CO.,Sudarwanto, AS 2016, the Mina Bahari '45 Cooperative has realized the goal of providing welfare for fishermen as its members in accordance with Law Number 25 of

1992 concerning Cooperatives and to improve the welfare of its members who work as fishermen, it is necessary to revitalize or strengthen the Mina Bahari '45 Cooperative. Integration between the government and cooperatives is carried out to carry out efforts to revitalize or strengthen cooperatives as legal entities. A cooperative is basically a social organization forum that prioritizes the social and economic interests of members by carrying out activities in accordance with the interests of members that are fostering and expanding their skills aimed at improving the welfare of members. Fishery cooperatives are an alternative that fishermen can choose to join in it. In addition, fishermen will also receive services from cooperatives, can improve welfare, make fisheries cooperatives a place to organize, broaden their horizons and information for the benefit of fishermen themselves.

Governments of developing countries support the formation of modern cooperative organizations and form specialized government agencies for them (such as departments, directorates, special services and agencies). This institution encourages the development of cooperatives that obtain funds from the state and the private sector to finance their activities into cooperative organizations (swadaya) that work efficiently and are member-oriented. The concept of business institution based on community participation is a main option to manage fisheries business in Laikang Village under "one direction". One of the best alternative of institution is developing fisheries cooperative, which is an evolution among business groups to become business units in fisheries cooperative (Zamroni, Achmad Istiana, Istiana, 2019).

Goals and usage

The aim is to find out how fisheries cooperatives are formed and how important the role of cooperatives is in the fisheries sector, knowing the important functions of cooperatives from both economic and social aspects.

METHODS

This research was conducted based on literature studies from several articles and books. The writing of this article is done by collecting information from various sources and then drawing conclusions from several articles that become references.

DISCUSSION

Definition of Cooperative

In general, in Indonesia, cooperatives are considered as social organizations, namely carrying out economic activities without seeking profit. There are also those who say that the cooperative is only for meeting the needs of its members. In Indonesian content, cooperatives are a legitimate form of business, whose existence is recognized in the 1945 Constitution.

For the Indonesian people, cooperatives are no longer strange, because we have experienced the services of cooperatives in order to get out of the difficulties of loan sharks. Literally Kpoerasi which comes from English

Cooperation consists of two syllables "Co" which means together "and" Operation "which means work". So cooperative means working together, so that every form of cooperation can be called a cooperative.

The definition of the main definition of cooperatives:

1. It is an association of people including legal entities that have the same interests and goals
2. Join themselves voluntarily as members and have the same rights and obligations as a reflection of democracy in the economy.
3. Losses and profits are shared and shared fairly.
4. Supervision is carried out by members.
5. Have the nature of helping each other.
6. Pay an amount of money as principal savings and mandatory savings as a condition of becoming a member.

In fact, even though a definition has many similarities, many people put emphasis on one of its elements. This depends on the different points of view of the life philosophy of people who put forward cooperatives, as a complement to the notion of cooperatives according to Law no. 12/1967 (first law regarding Indonesian Cooperatives)

The understanding of cooperatives according to experts, namely:

1. Article 1 No. RI Law No. 25 of 1992 concerning cooperatives. Affirming that what is meant by cooperatives is a business entity whose members are individual or cooperative legal entities by basing its activities on the principles of cooperatives as well as a people's economic movement based on the principle of kinship
2. According to Law no. 25 1992
Cooperatives are business entities whose members are individual persons or cooperative legal entities, by basing their activities on the cooperative principle as well as a people's economic movement, which is based on the principle of kinship.
3. Drs. Arifinal Chaniago (1984) in his book Indonesian Cooperatives
A cooperative is an association whose members are people or legal entities that give freedom of entry and exit as members by working together in a family way to enhance the physical welfare of its members "

Fisheries Cooperative

Based on PP 60 of 1959 concerning the Development of the Cooperative Movement, it is necessary to adjust the function of cooperatives as in principle regulated in the Cooperative Law with the spirit of the 1945 Constitution and the Political Manifesto of the President of the Republic of Indonesia dated 17 August 1959, where cooperatives must be given such a role. such that the movement and its implementation can actually constitute:

1. tools for implementing a guided economy based on Indonesian-style socialism;

2. joints of the economic life of the Indonesian nation,
3. the basis for regulating the people's economy in order to achieve a decent standard of living in a democratic just and prosperous society structure.

The government is obliged to take an active stance in fostering the Cooperative Movement based on the principles of Guided Democracy and it is necessary to issue a Government Regulation to adjust the implementation of the Cooperative Law with the 1945 Constitution and the Political Manifesto of the President of the Republic of Indonesia dated 17 August 1959, to grow, encourage, guide, protect and supervise the development of the Cooperative Movement; so that it is guaranteed, maintained and fostered dynamics both among the community itself and among state officials, as well as the operation of cooperatives simultaneously, intensively, planning and guided.

Based on PP 60 of 1959 concerning the Development of the Cooperative Movement part II concerning the classification of cooperatives which is a differentiation of cooperatives based on economic groups and functions. In this regulation, the basis for defining cooperatives is emphasized on the business field and the residence of members of a cooperative. Article 3 of this regulation prioritises the establishment of the following types of cooperatives:

1. Village Cooperative
2. Agricultural Cooperative
3. Animal Husbandry Cooperative
4. Fisheries Cooperative
5. Craft / Industrial Cooperative
6. Savings and Loans Cooperative

Referred to as Fisheries Cooperatives are cooperatives whose members consist of entrepreneurs who own fishing equipment, laborers / fishermen whose interests and livelihoods are directly related to the fishery business concerned and run businesses that are directly related to fishery business. from production, processing to buying or selling together the products of the fishery business concerned. According to Simbolon, S. (2018), that cooperatives in Tangerang district are still far from expectations in carrying out their duties in accordance with Article 33 of the UUD45 and / or the Cooperative Law, namely as economic teachers. In fact, with the current era of globalization, cooperatives tend not to be able to move independently, unless they are assisted by government policies.

The classification of cooperatives is based on economic groups and functions. However, to make it easier for the people, the type of cooperative according to this regulation is emphasized on the business field and the residence of the members. Thus, even though this Regulation is based on the business field and / or the residence of the members, provided that this paragraph is open the possibility for the community to organize types of cooperatives based on economic groups and functions.

Based on Law No. 16 of 1964 on Fishery Production Sharing, it is an effort towards the realization of the Indonesian socialist society in general,

especially to improve the standard of living of fishermen who cultivate and cultivate fish ponds and increase fish production, thus sharing fisheries, both fisheries. sea and land fisheries, must be regulated so that extortion elements are removed and all the participating parties each receive a fair share of the effort, also improvements to the terms of the production sharing agreement as intended above also need to be intensified. efforts to establish fishery cooperatives, whose members consist of all those who participate in the fishery business.

As one of the efforts towards the realization of an Indonesian socialist society in general to improve the living standards of fishermen and fishpond cultivators and to increase fish production, the Provisional People's Consultative Assembly in Decree No. II./MPRS/1960 and Resolution No. I / MPRS / 1963 ordered the issuance of a law regulating fishery business matters conducted under a production sharing agreement. This law is the realization of the MPRS order. As stipulated in article 12 paragraph 1 of the Basic Agrarian Law, all joint efforts in the agrarian field, including fisheries, both marine and land fisheries must be carried out based on the common interest of all participating parties, namely fishermen who own and own ponds who provide boats / boats, fishing gear and ponds as well as fishermen who work and cultivate the ponds who contribute their labor, until they each receive a fair share of the proceeds of the business. According to Sukardi, D., K., & Alifah, LN (2017)

Fisheries exploitation on the basis of current production sharing is carried out according to the provisions of local customary law which according to the standards of Indonesian socialism have not provided and become an appropriate share for fishermen who cultivate and cultivate ponds. In connection with this, it is necessary first of all to make provisions to eliminate the elements of the profit sharing agreement which are extortionate in nature, so that all parties who participate in the business receive a share in accordance with the services they contribute. By providing such a guarantee, in addition to improving the standard of living of the fishermen who cultivate and cultivate the pond concerned. it is also hoped that the emergence of a greater stimulant in increasing fish production. In that it is meaningless, that the interests of the owners of ships / boats, fishing gear and ponds will be ignored. Fishery business, especially marine fisheries, requires the use of tools that require maintenance and repair costs and which in time must be replaced with new ones. Assigning a proportion that is too small for the ordinary owner means that the matter of maintaining and repairing and replacing these tools will receive little or no attention. This also has an adverse effect on fish production in general. In this connection, the owners must also receive an appropriate share, with the understanding that in this way they are also obliged to carry out maintenance and repairs accordingly. Fishing tools and ponds will be neglected. Fishery business, especially marine fisheries, requires the use of tools that require maintenance and repair costs and which in time must be replaced with new ones. Assigning a proportion that is too small for the ordinary owner means that the matter of maintaining and repairing and replacing these tools will receive little or no attention. This also has an adverse effect on fish production in general. In this connection, the owners must also

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In the meantime, improving the standard of living of the fishermen and cultivators of tambak cannot be achieved only by improving the terms of the production sharing agreement. For this reason, efforts to form fishery cooperatives need to be intensified and the business field and membership need to be expanded. The membership of the cooperative must include all people who take part in the fishery business, so both cultivators, fishpond cultivators, fishery laborers and fishermen who own and own the pond. The fishery cooperative business field should not be limited to matters of production, for example the purchase of ships / boats and fishing gear, fish processing and marketing, but must also include matters of credit and matters relating to the welfare of members and his family. For example, efforts to meet daily needs, organizing accidents, deaths and others. In this way they can be released and avoided from the practices of moneylenders. middlemen and others, who are currently very rampant among fisheries businesses, especially marine fisheries. According to the current customary law, there is no

uniformity regarding the proportion of the share of the owner on the one hand and the fishermen who cultivate and cultivate the pond on the other. The difference is caused in addition to the balance between the number of fishermen working and cultivating the pond on the one hand as well as ships / boats, and the ponds will be shared on the other side, as well as by various other factors. Among them is the determination of what costs are shared and what each one of them carried. Regarding inland fisheries in the located ponds, the extent of the fertility conditions of the ponds and the types of fish produced are also factors that determine the proportion of the intended portion. If the pond is fertile, then the share of the owner is greater than that of the less fertile pond owner. Regarding marine fisheries, the types of boats, boats and fishing gears and methods used are also factors that determine the magnitude of the balance. The share of a motor boat owner, for example, is the greater the proportion. when compared to the part of a sailboat owner.

This is because the exploitation costs that must be incurred by the owner of the motorbike are greater, after all, the overall catch is greater, so that even though the percentage balance for working fishermen is smaller, the actual results received by each of them are greater when compared to the results of the working fishermen who use ships / sailboats. boats and fishing gears and methods used are also factors that determine the amount of the balance. The share of a motor boat owner, for example, is the greater the proportion. when compared to the part of a sailboat owner. This is because the exploitation costs that must be incurred by the owner of the motorbike are greater, after all, the overall catch is greater, so that even though the percentage balance for working fishermen is smaller, the actual results received by each of them are greater when compared to the results of the working fishermen who use ships / sailboats. boats and fishing gears and methods used are also factors that determine the amount of the balance.

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In this law, the part that must be given to fishermen who cultivate and cultivate ponds as stated in article 3, is determined on the basis of a balance in

the distribution of business burdens and costs as stated in article 4. In the regions Where the distribution of burdens and costs is in accordance with what is stipulated in Article 4, then only the regulations regarding the distribution of the results must be adjusted, that is, if according to local customs the share of the fishermen or cultivators of the pond is still less than what is stipulated. in article 3. If their share is greater than that stipulated in article 3, then the rules are more favorable the fishermen who cultivate or cultivate the pond should be used (Article 5 paragraph 1).

With such regulation, the provisions on profit sharing contained in this Law can be implemented immediately after this Law comes into effect, without completely precluding the possibility of making adjustments to regional conditions, if it is indeed true. necessary (article 5 paragraph 2). Regarding land fisheries, it is only given provisions regarding the implementation of fishpond production sharing, namely puddles created by people along the coast to raise fish, with regular irrigation. The business of raising fish in freshwater ponds and others is not subject to this law because generally it is not carried out by sharing, but is done by the owner himself. If there is maintenance that is carried out on a profit-sharing basis then it is about the pools that are not large. If there is a rice field that is divided into production and besides being planted with rice, there is also a fish farming business.

Benefits of Fisheries Cooperative

According to Wijayanto, D. (2015) Cooperatives are one of the backbones of the national economy, including fisheries cooperatives. In the era of regional autonomy, some fishery cooperatives experienced a decline in performance because they were no longer given the authority to manage fish auction places. Economically, the existence of the cooperative makes economic activities in the local community run smoothly. Several indicators that can be seen include:

1. It is easy for fishermen to sell their catch at a fairer price, because of the Fish Auction Place (TPI) which is managed by the Cooperative
2. The availability of ice as one of the main raw materials in the continuous fishing unit from the ice factory built by the Cooperative, so that fishermen do not go far to get ice from Peru.
3. The construction of a cooperative fish packing place facilitates the marketing process of the fishermen's catch, because the product can be packaged better and avoid damage.
4. The provision of credit by cooperatives is very helpful for fishermen, traders or baskets, and processing fishery products to develop their business.
5. The existence of SPDN as a fuel provider for fishermen is very helpful, because the price of fuel is set to be cheaper and available smoothly, all of which make fishing efforts efficient.
6. The provision of fishing gear (BAP) really helps fishermen to get fishing equipment at a cheaper price and can be obtained quickly, when compared to fishermen having to go to other areas.

7. The provision of telecommunication services, shops and food courts by the cooperative makes it easy for the community in balanakan to gain access to communication and necessities of daily goods.

According to Septiasari, Melita Darmawan, Dwi Suarthana, 2015, balanced score card should begin to be applied as a measure of performance in each of the cooperative in order to compete with their economic institutions. Apart from cooperatives, the government is expected to issue a policy that is balanced scorecard used as a strategy asked to be implemented by the cooperative. Socially, the role of cooperatives in regional development is no less important than its economic role, both in the fields of education, health and in other community activities. Some things that can be mentioned include:

1. The construction of worship facilities (mosques) and coaching of majelis taklim by cooperatives help the community to carry out their prayers properly
2. Provision of land for the construction of elementary schools (SD) and scholarships in collaboration with private organizations also play a role in improving the quality of human resources for fishermen's children.
3. The provision of housing for fishermen has also helped fishermen to obtain basic needs for housing.
4. In community activities, many cooperatives are orderly in organizing parties which are routinely held by the fishing community every year such as the Fishermen's Party.
5. The cooperative also provides compensation to elderly orphans, distributing food aid and famine funds for fishermen, fostering groups of fishermen and fisherwomen, as well as socializing legal awareness.
6. In the health sector, he is also involved in the provision of clean water, family planning activities, blood donation, posyandu, among others by providing Posyandu land, and contributing to the success of the National Immunization Week (PIN) program.

CONCLUSION

The existence of fisheries cooperatives is very helpful in meeting the needs of its members and the surrounding community such as basic assistance, capital, credit, or borrowing, sales, fishermen's needs in fishing and so on. The existence of cooperatives also provides benefits in other fields, such as education, community infrastructure development, health and various community activities.

SUGGESTION

In its implementation, cooperatives still have many shortcomings and obstacles, so that to overcome them, it is necessary to strengthen cooperative management, strengthen capital, increase awareness of the fisheries community regarding the importance of cooperatives and realize the government's side of fisheries cooperatives.

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